

MODERN TENDENCIES OF SCHOOL EDUCATION AND THE NEW STAGE OF REFORMS IN THE REGION OF NAVOI

Shirinova Firuza Inoyatovna

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Senior teacher of the Faculty of History.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10083031>

ANNOTATION: This article discusses the state policy on the issue of youth education, reforms in the activity of pre-school educational organizations, which are the first link of education, their results, and the work being carried out in Navoi region. Also, issues of implementation of the tasks specified in the "Bolajon" State Program in Navoi region were revealed.

Key words: education, program, reform, local bodies, young generation, kindergarten, home kindergartens.

President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev firmly appealed to the successors of our future that we will build a new Uzbekistan together with our determined young people. "We will provide quality education to the young generation in kindergarten, school and university, we will mobilize all our strength and opportunities so that they grow up to be physically and spiritually healthy, patriotic people"¹Therefore, education and upbringing will remain the first-level issue in human development. Pre-school education is definitely the first stage of education. The reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan in this regard are primarily aimed at the new development of education, legal protection and enrichment with foreign experiences. A new preschool education program has been developed in our country, which includes modern trends of education and new methods and technologies of teaching. Within this program, children gained knowledge and skills in language, mathematics, visual arts, physical education and other subjects, special attention was paid to the development of children's speech, thinking, attention and memory. For this, additional training and activities aimed at developing these skills were held. Attention was paid to the training and improvement of the skills of specialist personnel. Problems related to the financing of educational institutions have significantly decreased, which has had a positive effect on the quality of education and the conditions for children in pre-school educational institutions²

In 2015, during the development and improvement of preschool education in Navoi region, the number of preschool educational institutions was 550, and the number of children attending preschool educational institutions was more than 50,000. A new program of pre-school education has been developed, which takes into account the modern trends of education, and introduces new teaching methods and technologies. Children gained knowledge and skills in language, mathematics, visual arts, physical education and other subjects. Special attention was paid to the development of the child's personality, the formation of his social and

¹ Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis and his speech at the Youth Forum of Uzbekistan. T.: "Publishing house image" 2021. B.11

² Current archive of the Department of Pre-School Education Educational Institutions of Navoi region. January 2017 report.

communicative abilities. In 2016, problems related to the financing of preschool educational institutions were significantly reduced, which had a positive effect on the quality of education and conditions for children in preschool educational institutions. Parents and caregivers also had less difficulty paying for their children's preschool education.

In 2017, one of the problematic situations was the provision of drinking water to the MTMs in the Navoi region. The problem of drinking water was solved in 12 institutions where water is transported. "Kindergartens are equipped with modern equipment and methodical demonstration tools are provided. Stylists and educators have their annual calendar work plan, their rich pedagogical experience has been popularized³

In the newly adopted and improved "Bolajon" Program, based on the Law "On Education", "Concept of Preschool Education" and "State Requirements for Preschool Education" (2013), intellectual and physical development of the child, in the spirit of national-cultural and universal values aspects of upbringing, preparation for school education were revised based on the principles of modern pedagogy and psychology. The indicators given in all areas of "State requirements for preschool education" were fully included in the improved "Bolajon" basic program.

The "Bolajon" state support program was approved by the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2010 and was developed on the basis of "State requirements for the development of preschool children"⁴ In the program, the necessary amount of knowledge, skills and skills that children of each age group should acquire by the end of the school year, based on the pedagogical tasks of social-emotional, speech, reading and literacy preparation of children from the first to 6-7 years of age, as well as mental development, is determined. The purpose of the program is to raise physically healthy children who can engage in conscious communication, and the task of the program is to create conditions for the child's free thinking, social-emotional maturity, protecting their health, and growing up as a perfect person in the future.⁵

The main tasks of the "Bolajon" state program are to ensure the general development of the child's personality in accordance with the directions of physical development, self-care and hygiene, social-emotional development, speech, reading and literacy preparation, cognitive process and the acquisition of knowledge about the environment.

The main tasks of the "Bolajon" state program are to ensure the general development of the child's personality in accordance with the directions of physical development, self-care and hygiene, social-emotional development, speech, reading and literacy preparation, cognitive process and the acquisition of knowledge about the environment⁶ This is done in preschool education organization № 7 in Navoi city, the requirements set to educate the child spiritually, ethically, aesthetically, instill a desire for books in the heart, to form the culture of early reading, enrich the national - cultural heritage, Uzbek folk oral creativity, folk games, music,

³ National Archive of Uzbekistan. Fund M-26, list 1, volume 53, sheet 13.

⁴ Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan Retraining of employees of pre-school educational institutions and improving their qualifications Republican Educational Methodology Center "Bolajon" base program Tashkent.: 2016., B-7.

⁵ Azamova M.N., Rahmankulov Z.A. Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan Retraining of employees of pre-school educational institutions and improving their qualifications Republican Educational Methodology Center "Bolajon" base program.Tashkent.: 2016., p. 6-7.

⁶ Azamova M.N., Rahmankulov Z.A. Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan Retraining of employees of pre-school educational institutions and improving their qualifications Republican Educational Methodology Center "Bolajon" base program.Tashkent.: 2016., p. 6-7.

dance, painting, clay work, appliqué, building-making sections are being filled. In the 3rd quarter of 2016, in the Navoi region, the high-target tasks of the program were determined. According to the annual plan of the regional construction department, the construction and repair works of preschool educational institutions were completed, and the equipment works were finished in November of this year. Navoi city MTM №5, Nurota District - MTM № 1, Nurota District № 2 MTM, Navoi City MTM №16, Zarafshan City - MTM №1, Konimekh District - MTM №9, Kyziltepa District - MTM №4, Karmana 5, Khatirchi district, 5, Navbahor district, 6.0 bln. Soum funds have been allocated⁷

At the end of 2016, 24 thousand 442 children were enrolled in 130 preschool educational institutions in the region. The number of children of kindergarten age is 65,896, and short-term groups have been established to expand the coverage. 1049 foster children were admitted to them.¹ In 2018, 25 and more short-term groups will be launched. As a result, 1000-1250 more children are expected to be enrolled in pre-school educational institutions. In the matter of heating the rooms where classes are conducted, the shortcomings indicated in the applications received by parents were eliminated⁸ 11.9 billion soms of funds were allocated to the construction and repair works of 10 preschool educational institutions in the 2017 plan, and all facilities were put into full use. In addition, under the 2018 Investment Program project, a total of 16 (12 reconstructions and 4 complete repairs) preschool educational institutions were built and repaired in the region.

In accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 2016 PQ-2707, a list of preschool educational institutions that will be newly built, capitally reconstructed and fully renovated in 2017-2021 has been determined. According to it, in the Navoi region in 2017-2021, 6,860 places are planned, 1 MTM (120 places) will be built anew, 31 MTM (3,360 places in total) will be reconstructed and 22 MTM (3,380 places) will be fully renovated. In accordance with the Investment program of 2017 and the program "Further development of the preschool education system", construction and repair works are being carried out in 10 preschool educational institutions in our region (4 reconstructions and 6 complete repairs). Soum funds have been directed.

In 2017, a total of 10 preschool educational institutions were reconstructed in the region. The new building of "Oftobjon" kindergarten with 120 places in Karmana district was commissioned. 1 billion The institution, established on the basis of state and local budget funds of 200 million soums, fully meets the requirements of the time. In November of this year, 2519 boys and girls were admitted to 18 kindergartens in Karmana district⁹

At the beginning of 2018, a total of 4,916 pre-school educational institutions were operating across the country, and a total of 650,000 children received education in order to teach children the secrets of knowledge, prepare them for life and develop their knowledge in groups, depending on their interests, and consolidate it in practice. 210 home kindergartens, 264 pre-school and primary educational complexes, more than 50 early childhood development centers have been established across the country. But in the following years, the number of children attending preschool educational institutions has halved. The fact that education in pre-school educational institutions was not carried out at the required level, parents lost confidence in kindergarten, many kindergarten buildings were empty, they were

⁷ Preschool education is the guarantee of a bright future. Friendship flag. / January 1, 2018. No. 1

⁸ Current archive of the Department of Preschool Education of Navoi region. 2018 report

⁹ Friendship flag. New building for children./2018. January 23, #7.

not used effectively, local governments did not create the necessary conditions for the operation of this system, the reason for this system's backwardness. In this situation, the issue of preparing for school has put many parents in a difficult situation. Studying this situation, the Ministry of Public Education managed to establish preschool educational institutions in new types of alternative forms on the basis of public-private partnership, to allocate the necessary credit funds, and secondly, to provide education and training to children, to establish kindergarten-school cooperation between parents.¹⁰

In conclusion, we can say that the National Program did not appear by itself, but was created out of necessity. It is now known and clear to what extent the educational system has progressed."¹¹ Pre-school educational institutions of the "home-kindergarten" type are still a new type of preschool educational institutions, the process of its formation is a long-term step-by-step process.

¹⁰ Current archive of the Department of Preschool Education of Navoi region. 2021 report

¹¹ Sharipov F. Development of public education system in Soviet Uzbekistan. T.:1977. 17th p

References:

1. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis and his speech at the Youth Forum of Uzbekistan. T.: "Publishing house image" 2021. B.11.
2. Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan Retraining of Pre-School Educational Institutions Staff and Improving Their Qualifications Republican Training and Methodology Center "Bolajon" Base Program Tashkent.: 2016., B-7.
3. The current archive of the Department of Preschool Education Educational Institutions of Navoi Region. January 2017 report.
4. National Archive of Uzbekistan. Fund M-26, list 1, volume 53, sheet 13. 5. Flag of friendship. New building for children. /2018. January 23, #7.
6. Preschool education is the guarantee of a bright future. Friendship flag. / January 1, 2018. No. 1
7. Current archive of the Department of Preschool Education of Navoi region. 2018 report.
8. Current archive of the Department of Preschool Education of Navoi region. 2021 report.
9. Sharipov F. Development of public education system in Soviet Uzbekistan. T.:1977. 17th p.
10. Сабирова, Н. Э. (2022). ПОСЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬНОСТЬ РАЗВИТИЯ ИСКУССТВА БАХШИ ХОРЕЗМА. Universum: филология и искусствоведение, (4 (94)), 36-40.
11. Ergashevna, S. N. (2021, November). Traditions of khorezm caliphate and their peculiarities. In Archive of Conferences (pp. 120-123).
12. Turdiyevna, K. Z., & Ruzimovna, K. G. (2021). The role of zoonyms in the expression of axiological content. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(10), 1430-1434.
13. Azamova M.N., Rahmankulov Z.A. Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan Retraining of employees of pre-school educational institutions and improving their qualifications Republican Educational Methodology Center "Bolajon" base program.Tashkent.: 2016., p. 6-7.
14. Mamatkadirovna A. K. et al. Translation as a Special Type of Language and Intercultural Communication //JournalNX. –C. 176-180
15. Mamatkadirovna K. N. Pedagogical Conditions for the Development of Intercultural Communication Among Students //Czech Journal of Multidisciplinary Innovations. – 2022. – T. 12. – C. 88-93.